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THE NORMATIVE IMPERATIVE OF GENDER EQUALITY AS A FACTOR FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH.

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Policy Statement

Over the last 30 years, there has been undeniable progress in terms of women's and girls' rights. Specifically, over the last 10 years, under the normative imperative of SDG 5 – gender equality – there has been an increase in school inclusion, a one-third reduction in childbirth mortality, greater female representation in parliaments, and a reduction in discriminatory laws. To continue expanding this promising reality, it is necessary to advance gender equality policies, specifically those focused on women's work and autonomy, as catalysts for countries' economic growth and progress in relation to all other SDGs.

Background

Gender policy refers to the set of actions and strategies that aim to promote equality between men and women by addressing gender-based inequalities and violence. This policy manifests itself at different levels, from international agreements and national legislation to local public policies and affirmative action in various sectors.

From a global perspective, international agreements and treaties, such as the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), stand out for setting targets and guidelines for gender equality and addressing issues such as access to education, health, work, and political participation. At the national level, laws and public policies are defined, such as the criminalization of gender-based political violence and programs to combat domestic violence, to guarantee women's rights and promote equality in this area. Locally, gender policies are manifested in actions such as the creation of reference centers for women in situations of violence, the promotion of women's empowerment projects, the guarantee of access to health and education services, and the inclusion of women in political and economic decision-making spaces.

Despite significant advances, the labor market still shows notable disparities between men and women across various professional areas. The discrepancy is due to the major obstacles women face, such as the wage gap, which directly affects access to education and professional development opportunities, creating financial difficulties. This inequality stems, in part, from the overload of responsibilities women face.

In addition to their professional activities, they often take on most of the household chores and childcare. The so-called “double shift” prevents women from devoting sufficient time and energy to advancing their careers.

In patriarchal cultures, gender stereotypes remain a significant obstacle. Preconceived notions suggest that women lack the necessary assertiveness, whereas men are considered better leaders due to their supposed ability to handle adverse situations. These stereotypes impede women's advancement in the labor market, reinforcing the idea that they are too emotional for the professional environment, even though evidence shows that women excel at managing emotions - a trait valued in today's market. Therefore, reducing inequalities can be effectively achieved only through cultural and structural transformations that extend beyond laws. To achieve this, mainstreaming gender, race, and class into public policies – across all sectors, not just specific policies for women - and recognizing the importance of women's policy organs (OPMs) in this effort is essential to changing the landscape of inequality between men and women, particularly in the workplace.

Findings

At the global and regional levels, according to the UN publication (2024) on the world of work, men accounted for 4.8% of the worldwide unemployment rate among people aged 15 and over, and women for 5.2%. Data concerning individuals who want but do not have a job showed the following breakdown by gender: 8.3% for men and 13% for women. From this, it can be inferred that, even if they want to, women are less likely than men to seek or be available, in a short period of time, to take up a position in the formal labor market. In Latin America and the Caribbean, these percentages are even more worrying: while unemployment among men stood at 5.2%, that of women reached 7.5%. Next, the gender gap in the unemployment rate is 9.5% for men and 19.3% for women. With these results, Latin America and the Caribbean are ahead of only Sub-Saharan Africa, North Africa, and Western Asia.

In light of the above, one critical point that cannot be ignored is the strong connection between education and gender equality. We are concerned that, globally, 39% of young women do not finish high school. Therefore, there is an urgent need for short- and medium-term policies that are proven to be gender-sensitive, such as lowering the cost of schooling through cash transfers to families to support girls' and women's education, creating safe environments, and implementing measures to prevent all

forms of gender-based violence (GBV); adopting a qualified gender approach related to the labor market to increase skills; conducting awareness campaigns; and reducing school dropout rates.

The UN also warns of the advance of Artificial Intelligence and agrees that this advance is reshaping the labor market. The same publication states that, in the period studied, 3.7% of women had jobs that could be replaced by technology. Among men, this rate was 1.4%. Another noteworthy warning is as follows: globally, women still spend, on average, 2.5 times more time per day on unpaid care and domestic work than men do on the same tasks (UN, 2024).

Worldwide, women account for only 35% of graduates in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. In this context, if the global gender gap in Internet use is not addressed, the cost to low- and middle-income countries could reach \$500 billion over the next five years. Furthermore, the United Nations points out that investing in the care sector could create approximately 300 million jobs worldwide by 2035 (UN, 2024).

Finally, it is noteworthy that less than 0.05% of projects involving statistics and data supported by public authorities address gender dimensions. For this and other equally important reasons, it is crucial to be aware of the specific gender indicators of the 2030 Agenda with regard to the labor market, which are listed below (UN, 2024).

Gender-specific indicators for SDG 5 – Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls:

- Existence of legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and monitor equality and non-discrimination based on sex.
- Proportion of time spent on unpaid domestic and care work, by sex, age, and location.
- Proportion of seats held by women in (a) national parliaments and (b) local governments.
- Proportion of women in management positions.
- Proportion of individuals who own a mobile phone, by sex.
- Promotion of systems to track and make public the resources allocated to gender equality and women's empowerment.
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Gender-specific indicators for SDG 8 – Promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all.

- Proportion of informal employment in total employment, by sector and sex.
- Average hourly earnings of male and female employees, by occupation and age. Unemployment rate, by sex and age.
- Proportion and number of children aged 5 to 17 involved in child labor, by sex and age.

In Brazil, according to research published by IBGE for the third quarter of 2024, the number of individuals of working age, or rather, people aged 14 or older, reached 81.2% of the total population. The Southeast region showed a percentage above the national average: 82.7% (IBGE, 2024b). Within this large group, the document presents, among other indices, the national unemployment rate by gender and by color or race. The unemployment rate by gender was 5.3% for men and 7.7% for women in the third quarter of 2024. The unemployment rate by color or race was below the national average for whites (5.0%) and above for blacks (7.6%) and browns (7.3%) (IBGE, 2024a).

For comparison purposes, it is worth mentioning that in the same period, in the state of Minas Gerais, “the unemployment rate was higher among women, reaching 6.2%, compared to 4.0% among men,” that is, it was lower than the national rates for both women and men (FJP, 2024). However, when we consider overall rates, as shown in the table below, Minas Gerais did not stand out among women as it did among men (UN, 2024). It should be noted that in that quarter, women accounted for 64% of the total number of individuals who did not make their labor available (FJP, 2024).

Unemployment rate by gender in 2024**		
Reference	Women	Men
Global (Jan to Sep 2024/UN)	5.20%	4.80%
Latin America and the Caribbean (Jan to Sep 2024/UN)	7.50%	5.20%
National (Jul to Sep 2024/IBGE)	7.70%	5.30%
Southeast (Jul to Sep 2024/IBGE)	7.60%	5.10%

Sources: UN (2024); IBGE (2024a) e FJP (2024).

Although the continuous PNAD for the fourth quarter of 2024 is already available, this study used the third quarter of 2024 to mirror the IBGE indices with those of the UN, using September 2024 as the reference month.

In addition to our focus on the inclusion of women in the workforce, this complements the “Women @ Work 2024” survey conducted by Deloitte, which interviewed 5,000 female workers across 10 countries and revealed equally worrying data. For example, 14% of respondents believe that women's rights deteriorated in their country of origin in the year before the survey. This figure rises to 17% in Brazil. Add to this the fact that while 52% of the 500 Brazilian respondents said they were concerned about women's rights, 49% feared for their personal safety and 48% for their financial security. Furthermore, the survey indicated that women in Brazil suffer more microaggressions (35%) than their counterparts in the other nine countries (31%) and that the rate of Brazilian women who file formal complaints of sexual harassment is 40% compared to 66% in the other participating countries. The reasons given for the 26% below-average rating were: concern that the situation would worsen (19%), fear that the complaint would not be taken seriously (17%), and fear of possible negative impacts on their careers (12%) (Deloitte, 2024).

There is no doubt that promoting gender equality is an essential item on the economic and social development agenda of any nation. However, despite the data illustrating the positive economic impact of women's inclusion in the labor market, other data presented here, among many others available, highlight the urgency and fundamental importance of overcoming the inequality that still challenges us.

The precarious working conditions faced by women, which are reflected in informal and vulnerable jobs, for example, are directly linked to wage inequality—women earn, on average, 77 cents for every dollar paid to men. This reality not only perpetuates inequality but also devalues the fundamental human potential that could contribute to increased productivity and innovation across various sectors of the economy. This assertion shows that addressing gender equality with seriousness and commitment goes beyond guaranteeing fundamental rights for women; it is about laying the necessary foundations for a prosperous and sustainable economic future.

In this perspective, it is essential to consider the institutional structures within the Executive Branch—federal, state, and municipal—that address inequalities between women and men and the implementation of public policies for women. At the federal level, the Ministry of Women promotes the creation of these institutions and provides general guidelines for their activities. In the states, Executive Bodies for Women's Policies, such as secretariats, undersecretariats, coordination offices, among others, are present in all Federation Units (RASEAM: 2025, p. 144).

However, according to the Annual Socioeconomic Report on Women (RASEAM: 2025), of the 27 federal units, only 15 states have secretariats exclusively dedicated to women's policies, and in four states, they are mixed bodies, that is, they deal with other policies as well, especially human rights and social assistance. Other significant information regarding the institutionalization of women's policy is that all federal units have a State Council for Women's Rights, and only seven—Tocantins, Ceará, Pernambuco, Rio de Janeiro, São Paulo, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul—reported not having a State Plan for Women's Policy.

Of the 5,570 municipalities, 18.3% have Secretariats for Women's Policies, most of which are concentrated in the Northeast (33.4% of the secretariats are in this region and represent 63.3% of the municipalities) and the North (27.1% of the secretariats, representing 11% of the municipalities). In the Southeast region of the state of Minas Gerais, 61 municipalities have OPMs for promoting gender equality. Among them, we can mention only four municipalities with secretariats for women's policies, namely Contagem (Municipal Secretariat for Women and Youth); Sete Lagoas (Municipal Secretariat for Women); José Gonçalves de Minas (Municipal Secretariat for Public Policies for Women), and Juiz de Fora (Special Secretariat for Women)[1].

Recommendations

The World Bank Group's (WBG) “Gender Strategy 2024–2030” establishes guidelines and objectives for promoting gender equality worldwide. Of the three main strategic goals outlined in the document, for the purposes of this study, our emphasis was on the second objective: boosting and expanding economic opportunities for women.

The document mentions that gender equality is a key factor for economic growth and productivity. It even states that if the female labor force were at the same rate as that of men, long-term per capita income could increase by up to 20%. In addition, the report argues that increasing equality in access to assets and economic participation not only contributes to poverty reduction but also positively affects overall financial performance. Therefore, the promotion of gender equality goes beyond ethical precepts of social justice, as it is considered a driver of economic development (WBG, 2024).

To achieve this goal, the Group proposes interventions through the following approaches:

- **Promoting access to quality jobs:** Ensuring that women have access to quality jobs and entrepreneurship opportunities. This includes reviewing restrictive laws and/or regulations, where applicable, improving employer policies and practices, and raising awareness of gender issues in the workforce.
- **Training and empowerment programs:** Develop training programs that support women's productive economic participation and entrepreneurship. This also includes strategies to increase women's access to and control over economic assets, such as land and technology.
- **Support services:** Plan and integrate “enabling services” that expand women’s economic choices and are adaptable to challenging contexts. These services may include safe transportation, access to digital technologies, and general care.
- **Changing norms and behaviors:** Involve men and boys in promoting gender equality and changing harmful social norms. This includes addressing attitudes and behaviors that limit women's economic participation and creating a culture that supports women's empowerment.
- **Public policy interventions:** Create policies and support reforms that establish gender equality in the economy, ensure protection against discrimination in the workplace, and foster conditions conducive to women's participation in emerging sectors such as renewable energy and technology.
- **Data and monitoring:** Use data and analysis to help identify the barriers faced by women in the labor market and monitor progress toward positive economic outcomes.

Final Considerations

The normative force of SDG 5 requires promoting social justice, sustainable development, and peace worldwide, recognizing that gender equality is a prerequisite for a better future for all. Promoting this equality means, among other things, eradicating poverty, since women and girls are disproportionately affected. Making policies to break the cycle of poverty is crucial; promoting access to quality education and healthcare supports their personal development and the growth of their communities; addressing violence against women and girls is essential to ensure peace and security as fundamental in building peaceful and just societies; sustainably managing natural resources helps foster adaptation to climate change; and economically empowering women acts as a driving force for inclusive and sustainable economic growth.

This paper has demonstrated that maritime governance can no longer be understood solely through traditional State-based models, nor by approaches centred exclusively on the logic of national sovereignty. The multiplicity of actors involved in oceanic dynamics necessitates a revision of conventional analytical frameworks, particularly those that have historically overlooked the fluidity, extraterritoriality, and relational nature of maritime spaces. Critical and constructivist approaches – by emphasising the intersubjectivity of actors and the plurality of rationalities involved – reveal that the sea is not merely a zone of geopolitical contestation. Still, also a space where power practices, forms of knowledge, and struggles for legitimacy are deeply intertwined.

Implementing effective gender policies requires a collaborative effort from governments, civil society, the private sector, and citizens. Ensuring gender equality at every level helps build more just, peaceful societies where human potential can be fully realized. According to the report **Women, Business and the Law** (WORLD BANK GROUP: 2024), gender equality in the labor market could boost global GDP by more than 20%, effectively doubling the global growth rate over the next decade. Investing in gender equality has proven to be an essential tool for promoting development, economic recovery, technological progress, and even preventing conflict. Mainstreaming gender policies in the labor market not only fosters justice and equality but also benefits businesses and society as a whole. Companies with diverse and inclusive teams tend to be more innovative, productive, and profitable. Additionally, gender equality supports the country's social and economic development, helping create a more just and egalitarian society.

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[1] The municipality of Conceição do Mato Dentro, with an estimated population of 24,000 inhabitants according to the IBGE in 2024, is the first mining municipality to create a Secretariat for Women's Policies with two main structural pillars in its organizational chart: Work and Autonomy, and Combating Violence against Women—the two sides of female autonomy.

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